

Supporting information for:

Blue-UV Emitting ZnSe(dot)/ZnS(rod) Core/Shell Nanocrystals Prepared from CdSe/CdS Nanocrystals by Sequential Cation Exchange

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EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Chemicals and synthesis procedures

Materials. Trioctylphosphine oxide (TOPO, 99%), Trioctylphosphine (TOP, 97%), Selenium (Se, 99.99%) and Sulfur (S, 99.99%) were purchased from Strem Chemicals. Octadecylphosphonic acid (ODPA, 99%) and Hexylphosphonic acid (HPA, 99%) were purchased from Polycarbon Industries. Cadmium oxide (CdO, 99.5%), Tetrakis(acetonitrile) Copper(I) Hexafluorophosphate ($[\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_4]\text{PF}_6$, 99.99%), Zinc chloride (ZnCl_2 , 99.999%), Oleylamine (OLAM, 70%), 1-Octadecene (ODE 90%), nonanoic acid (98%), 2-aminopyridine (99%), Toluene (Analysis grade), Hexane (Analysis grade), and Tetrachloroethylene (TCE, spectroscopic grade) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All chemicals were used as received.

Synthesis of CdSe/CdS core/shell NRs in detail. CdSe/CdS core/shell NRs were synthesized according to a literature method developed by Carbone et al.¹ Firstly; the CdSe seeds with different sizes were prepared by changing the injection temperature and the growth time. In detail, 3 g TOPO, 0.280 g ODPA and 0.060 g CdO were mixed in a 50mL flask, heated to 120°C and purged under vacuum for 1 hour. Then, under nitrogen, the solution was heated to 370°C to dissolve the CdO until it turned optically clear and colourless. At this point, the injection of the Se:TOP solution (0.058 g Se + 0.360 g TOP) was performed. The reaction was stopped after 1 minute by removing the heating mantle. In this case the size of CdSe NCs is around 5.0 nm. The obtained CdSe Seeds were purified by repeated cleaning and were then dispersed in TOP. Secondly, CdSe/CdS core/shell NRs were prepared by using the obtained CdSe NCs as the seeds. In detail, a mixture of HPA (67 mg), ODPA (333 mg), TOPO (3g), and CdO (0.1 g) was first degassed in a 50 mL three-neck flask at room temperature in vacuum and subsequently at 120°C for 60 min. It was then slowly heated under N_2 until CdO was decomposed and the solution

turned clear. When the temperature reached 350°C, the injection solution was prepared by mixing 200 µL CdSe seeds solution as we have prepared above and sulfur (100 mg) dissolved in TOP (1.5 mL), which were rapidly injected into the vigorously stirred Cd precursor. The CdSe/CdS NRs were allowed to grow for 5 minutes. The length and the thickness of the final CdSe/CdS rods can be tuned by the amount of the used sulphur and the CdSe seed.

Cation exchange reactions from the ZnSe/ZnS core/shell NRs to CdSe/CdS core/shell NRs

(Figure 3). To test the overall preservation of the Se/S anion sublattice in the NRs, we re-converted the obtained ZnSe/ZnS NRs sample into CdSe/CdS NRs by two reverse steps of CE, namely $\text{Zn}^{2+} \Rightarrow \text{Cu}^+$ followed by $\text{Cu}^+ \Rightarrow \text{Cd}^{2+}$. In the first $\text{Zn}^{2+} \Rightarrow \text{Cu}^+$ step, the obtained ZnSe/ZnS NRs were dispersed in toluene after the cleaning procedure, and the solution of $[\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_4]\text{PF}_6$ (dissolved in methanol) were added into the above solution of ZnSe/ZnS NRs. After the reaction, the obtained $\text{Cu}_2\text{Se}/\text{Cu}_2\text{S}$ NRs were washed two times to remove the additional precursor. ICP analysis on the $\text{Cu}_2\text{Se}/\text{Cu}_2\text{S}$ NRs indicate that the transformation from $\text{Zn}^{2+} \Rightarrow \text{Cu}^+$ is completed and the atom ratio of $\text{Cu}/(\text{Se}+\text{S})$ is 2:1. After that the $\text{Cu}_2\text{Se}/\text{Cu}_2\text{S}$ NRs were suspended in 2 mL TOP. For the second step of $\text{Cu}^+ \Rightarrow \text{Cd}^{2+}$ cation exchange reaction, we prepared the solution of Cd^{2+} cation by dissolving 0.5 mmol CdO in a solution of 4 mL degassed octadecene and 2 mmol nonanoic acid at 150 C. The above $\text{Cu}_2\text{Se}/\text{Cu}_2\text{S}$ NRs obtained in the first $\text{Zn}^{2+} \Rightarrow \text{Cu}^+$ step were injected into the Cd^{2+} cation solution. The cation exchange reaction from Cu^+ to Cd^{2+} can be finished in 10 seconds, as could be clearly assessed by observing the colour changing in the solution after the injection of $\text{Cu}_2\text{Se}/\text{Cu}_2\text{S}$ NRs. After the synthesis, the CdSe/CdS NRs were precipitated with methanol; they were washed by repeated re-dissolution in toluene and precipitation with the addition of methanol, and were finally dissolved in toluene.

Figure S1. In some cases, ZnSe/ZnS NRs with defect emission were observed in our synthesis. These NRs were formed when the reaction temperature was 150°C and the Zn/Cu ratio that we used was below 50. Two samples of ZnSe/ZnS NRs in this case have the same length (33 nm) and core sizes equal to 3.0 nm (a) and 5.0 nm (b). Their defect emissions are located at around 420 nm (a) and 450 nm (b), respectively.

Figure S2. The stability of the ZnSe/ZnS NRs was investigated by tracing their PL after they were exposed to air. The ZnSe/ZnS NRs were dispersed in toluene and kept under air for three days. Their PL spectra were recorded at various time intervals. The changes of the concentrations due to the very slowly evaporation of the solvent were also taken into account by adding a few drops of toluene before each measurement to make sure that volume of the solution was the same in all the measurements.

Figure S3. EDS spectra (in the spectral region of interest) summed over several ZnSe/ZnS NRs (the same NRs as in Figure 1c of the work) show a low residual Cd and Cu content after the sequential cation exchange reactions. The atomic ratio measured in the particles, carried out using the peaks labeled in red in the plot, is Zn : S : Se = 52 : 42 : 6 (the signals of Cd and Cu lie within the background noise). In particular, the Se/S atomic ratio is consistent with the ~10% core/rod volume ratio. The signal from Ni is due to the TEM support grid.

Figure S4. Mean dilation maps obtained from HRTEM images of ZnSe/ZnS NRs (the same sample as that shown in Figure 1c of the work) by means of the peak pairs algorithm (PPA) for strain calculation.² The scale bar and the color scale used for dilation amplitude are identical for all the images (-6% min., +12% max.). In each image the average value for the mean dilation measured in the rod core with respect to the unstrained wurtzite ZnS portion of the rod is shown. The average dilation, evaluated from these and additional HRTEM images, is $3.9(\pm 0.9)\%$, consistent with the expected 4% lattice mismatch between wurtzite ZnSe and wurtzite ZnS.

Figure S5. (Top) HRTEM image of a CdSe/CdS NR from the starting sample for the sequential cation exchange (the same sample as that shown in Figure 1a of the work). Only the lattice spacings of wurtzite (w) CdS are measured (see higher magnification image and FFT in the central insets) due to the superimposition of the CdS and CdSe structures in the core region. At one extreme of the core region a structural defect is visible, consisting of few planes arranged according to the sphalerite (s) structure. (Bottom) Mean dilation maps obtained from the same image by PPA analysis show an average dilation in the core of $3(\pm 1)\%$ with respect to unstrained CdS, in agreement with the expected 4% lattice mismatch between wurtzite CdSe and wurtzite CdS, indicating that the dilated region corresponds to the wurtzite CdSe core. This result confirms the reliability of the PPA method for the identification of the ZnSe cores inside

the ZnSe/ZnS NRs. The color scale used for dilation amplitude is identical as for the dilation maps of ZnSe/ZnS NRs (-6% min., +12% max.).

Figure S6. Examples of time resolved photoluminescence decay for two ZnSe/ZnS NRs samples having 5.0 nm (a) and 2.3 nm (b) cores. The emission was spectrally integrated around the emission peak over ± 20 nm, for (a) and ± 10 nm for (b). The solid line is the bi-exponential fit (a small background was also added in (a)). Data points around the laser excitation pulse (in grey), show the finite instrumental response in this long time range and have been discarded for fitting purposes. Short decay components have been confirmed via further measurements and fitting at higher temporal resolution (shorter time range) not reported here.

References

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